

Reservoir-Induced Alterations and Climate Change Effects: A Case Study of Alaknanda River Basin

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ABSTRACT

The Bhagiratha brought the nectar from heaven and the fortunate Himalaya let it flow over its valleys and recharge throughout the year with the help of south-western monsoon and westerlies. The sacred Ganga, descending from the heavens through the Himalayan valleys, nourishes the land with its perennial flow, fed by the monsoon and the westerlies. But the river basin faces many challenges in the modern world, from pollution to climate change. The lower stretches of the river are tainted by urban waste, while the upper reaches are prone to floods and flash floods that cleanse the river but also cause havoc and destruction. The Kedarnath Disaster (2013) is a grim reminder of the river's wrath. The river basin receives abundant rainfall and snowmelt from both sides of the orographic barrier (i.e. main central thrust zone), which affects the water volume and discharge. This study explores the relationship between the discharge and the disasters (or the extreme events) that occurred in the Upper Ganga River Basin. The data from stations Karnaprayag, Rudraprayag (Alaknanda), Rudraprayag (Mandakini), Chandrapuri, Tehri and Devprayag show that the orographic front side had high discharge values in the years 1998, 2005 and 2010, which coincided with several reported extreme events. The results suggest that the anomalously high discharge value is a good indicator of an extreme event in the region. This indicator can be used as a warning signal for future disasters and to plan for mitigation and management strategies.

Key words: Ganga, discharge, extreme event, precipitation pattern.

INTRODUCTION

The Himalayan River systems have nearly double sediment erosion rate as of any compare to any other river system (Singh and Hasnian 1999). This erosion is attributed to high relief, steep gradient, favourable rock type, intense precipitation, glacial activities and so on. The erosion of sediment is an extensive and slow process where the precipitation and the glacial inputs are generally cyclic. There are a number of recorded events (e.g. Kedarnath Floods in 2013) when a thick pile of sediments is deposited in just couple of days (e.g. as thick as 10 m at Sonprayag; Devrani et al. 2015) due to swift weather changes in the precipitation resulted as cloud bursting. In the Himalayas, this anomalous sedimentation is generally recoded during the south-western Monsoon (generally June to September). This phenomenon is taking place because the basin gets a major part of total precipitation in just one third period of the year, except the water added by westerlies and snow melt. The natural disasters like flash floods and landslide in the Ganga River basin are mostly consequences of extreme events (Paul et al. 2000; Naithani et al. 2002, 2011; Kumar et al. 2007; Gupta and Bist 2004; Rana et al.

2012; Dubey et al. 2013; Gupta et al. 2013) added with snow melting at high reaches (Rautela and Thakur 1999; Naithani 2001; Singh et al. 2005; Rana et al. 2012) and natural damming of the river (Paul et al. 2000; Sati et al. 2011).

The wet season of the year also affect the area or especially the slopes of the area in two ways, firstly the excess pore water increases the pressure along with lubrication of the incompetent layer and secondly the sudden rise in stream water level initiate the toe cutting of slopes. This slope failure mechanism turns-out in natural damming (landslide damming) and the sudden bursting of the same increases the sediment load and erosion in the basin.

The present study is an attempt to predict the natural disasters with the help of precipitation outcomes, i.e. water discharge and sediment yield. The observations are also strengthened by the analysis of precipitation trend in the study area.

STUDY AREA

The South Asian Sub-continent is fed by a number of rivers and the Ganges covers third most important part with 8.61×10^3 km² area. The lower reaches of the basin is experiencing flood almost every year, probably due to

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climatic changes and the interference of anthropological elements in the flow region. In the recent past, the encroachment in the upper river valley, to harness the energy and to enhance tourism, has made the situation even worse. So, the major emphasis in the present study is given to the major two river valleys, Alaknanda and Bhagirathi (30°-31°N latitudes and 78°45'-80°E longitudes), where the extreme events and resultant disasters are frequently witnessed.

This area is regionally known as *Garhwal Himalaya* and is sandwiched between the Tibetan plateau and Indo-Gangetic Plains on the north and south respectively. The area covers eight major districts of Uttarakhand state of India and the catchment area is about $11.08 \times 10^3 \text{ km}^2$ and $7.65 \times 10^3 \text{ km}^2$ for Alaknanda and Bhagirathi Rivers respectively. The geology of area has been studied intensively since 1885 by Middlemiss and the stratigraphic successions are

established after Auden in 1934 which was further refined by a number of subsequent workers (i.e. Heim and Gansser 1939; Jain 1971; Rupke 1974; Valdiya 1980, 1995; Srivastava and Mitra 1994; Richards et al. 2005, Yin 2006). The study area consists of three geological domains, firstly, the Trans Himalayan Sedimentary sequence is bounded by South Tibetan Detachment Sequence (STDS; Le Fort 1996) and lies on the southern edge of the Tibetan plateau and in the northern part of the Garhwal Himalaya. This area receives scanty rainfall due to the presence of the Higher Himalayan series which prevents the moisture-laden winds from migrating further northward. The second downhill is the Higher Himalayan Crystalline Series, bounded by MCT (main central thrust) in the south (Coleman 1998) and consists of the medium to high-grade metamorphic rocks belonging to the Vaikrita Group and Munsiri formations (Patel and Carter 2009) with pro-grade metamorphism (Vannay et al. 2004) at places.

Figure 1: Map showing the rainfall distribution and location of reported landslides and extreme events in the study area.

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Finally, towards the foothill side, the Lesser Himalayan Crystalline and Sedimentary are bounded between the MCT II (Munsiari Thrust) in the north and MBT (main boundary thrust) in the south and consist of medium to low-grade metamorphics, calc-silicates, impure limestone and dolomites (Valdiya 1995).

There are several local and regional faults and other structural deformations existing in the study area (Thakur 1992; Rajendran et al. 2000; Celerier et al. 2009, 2010) which also affects the discharge and sediment production in the basin.

METHODOLOGY

The specific sediment yield is calculated according to Haritashya et al. (2006) and Holeman (1968) method with

the help of about 34 years (1976-2010) annual river discharge and sediment load data collected by CWC (Central Water Commission) observation stations. Data of the nine observation stations have been selected for the analysis, i.e. Badrinath, Joshimath, Rudraprayag in Alaknanda River; Uttarkashi, Tehri and Devprayag in Bhagirathi River; Chandrapuri and Rudraprayag stations in the tributary of Mandakini River and Karnaprayag in Pinder river (a tributary of Alaknanda River).

The precipitation data is collected from TRMM (Tropical Rainfall Measurement Mission), which is about 40% of the observed data so it is further standardised with the help of observed precipitation data of 1998, 2005 and 2010 collected from IMD (Indian Meteorological Department).

Figure 2: TRMM precipitation data (1998-1999) plotted over the longitudinal profile of the Bhagirathi River, depicting MCT as an orographic barrier (note the peaks in front of MCT).

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The present study analyses the contribution of monsoonal rainfall in the disasters that took place in the basin. However, at the same time high values of river discharge and sediment load contributed from the glacial melts cannot be ruled out, especially in Chorbari Bamak glacier, Satopanth and Bhagirathi Kharak Glacier, Khatling Glacier, Tiprabamak Glacier, Gangotri and Dokraini glacial region. It is also noticed that in the years 1998, 2005 and 2010 the area received high river discharge and sediment loads

which could be cumulative effect of high glacial melt and high precipitations.

The results shows that on an average per year 5.42×10^6 ton of sediment is eroded from the Bhagirathi River Basin but it shows an anomalously high value of about 2.5 times in 2010. Such anomalous increase have also been observed in 1998 and 2005. The annual sediment erosion is comparatively high in Alaknanda River Basin (6.17×10^6 ton) and the anomalous increase is observed in the same years as witnessed in Bhagirathi River Basin, which is highest (~1.5 times) in year 2010. The data suggests a

positive correlation between the discharge and sediment load, moreover the trend is almost similar. Though, some specific storm events have also been documented with anomalously high discharge (as high as 1208m³/s in July, 1998) as compared to the average monthly discharge of 119 m³/s.

In the study area, a total of 31 extreme events and 308 landslides have been recorded and/or observed. Among them, half (13) were witnessed during 1998, 2005 and 2010. The steep slopes in the study area also show some failure incidents in the aforesaid period.

If, extreme events and landslide incidents show a positive correlation with discharge and sediment load, it can be directly correlated with the precipitation as well. So, the discharge of the river can be used as a tool for predicting a disaster which is going to happen in the area.

flood (GLOF) during the monsoon, among them, the Kedarnath Disaster can be cited as the recent one. The analysis of the precipitation, discharge and sediment load data from different stations in the concerned basins relates well with the occurrences of extreme event instances. The assimilation of the various relationships drawn among the operating factors and the resultants provided significant insight into the existing knowledge.

The present communication reveals a fair agreement between the high discharge and the subsequent high sediment load and the occurrence of extreme events. So, the anomalously high values of both the discharge and sediment load for a particular location can be treated as a signature or signal for an extreme event that is a preparatory phase and may take place.

In the present scenario, where the humans have penetrated deeply into the natural balance, the effects of extreme events are exaggerated to a great extent. Such in-depth studies on are required to predict the phenomenon and to suggest preventive measures to deal with or minimize the damage to life and property in the Indian Himalayan region for future. So, the utilization of the outcomes of the present research can be utilized as a forewarning to the upcoming devastating extreme event.

Figure 3: Graphs showing the positive correlation between the discharge and sediment load data (note the peaks correlate well the extreme events of 1998, 2005 and 2010.)

CONCLUSION

As discussed in the previous sections, the Garhwal Himalayas have witnessed numerous intense mass instability and metrological disasters such as flash floods, cloud bursts and glacier avalanches or glacial lake outburst

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